

C-SCALE

D3.7 Final assessment of the services

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Deliverable Abstract

This report presents the final assessment of the C-SCALE services provided through the Virtual Access (VA) mechanism to the users. These include computing and storage resources. The deliverable describes the existing VA installations, and their management within the project, updates the usage metrics delivered from the start of the project (January 2021) until Month 33 (September 2023) and reports on the Green Computing metrics and initiatives from the C-SCALE providers.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
CO	Collaborative Organisation
C-SCALE	Copernicus - eoSC AnaLytics Engine
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
EO	Earth Observation
EODC	Earth Observation Data Centre (C-SCALE provider)
EO-MQS	Earth Observation Metadata Query Service
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC DIH	European Open Science Cloud - Digital Innovation Hub
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GRNET	National Infrastructures for Research and Technology (C-SCALE provider)
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HiSea	High Resolution Copernicus-Based Information Services at Sea for Ports and Aquaculture
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTC	High Throughput Computing
HTDP	High Throughput Data Processing
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
INCD-NCG	Infraestrutura Nacional de Computação Distribuída-National Computing Grid (C-SCALE provider)
OLA	Operational Level Agreement
OPEX	Operating Expense
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PBS	Portable Batch System
PUE	Power usage effectiveness
REF	Renewable energy factor

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SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SRAM	SURF Research Access Management
STAC	Spatio Temporal Asset Catalog
TB	Terabyte
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VA	Virtual Access
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

C-SCALE brings together European commercial (e.g., Copernicus DIAS) and public computing and storage providers to deliver a federated infrastructure to support Copernicus and Earth Observation (EO) use cases dealing with data- and compute-intensive workloads. The federation enables the access to a set of computing and storage resources, called *installations*, operated by the partners of the project, and deployed via a Virtual Access mechanism. Almost 20% of the total C-SCALE budget was devoted to cover the costs of these installations that the project has delivered to EOSC users as services.

This document updates the previous reports provided in Month 24 (December 2022), Month 18 (June 2022) and in Month 14 (February 2022) – originally planned in Month 12 (December 2021) – on the usage of Virtual Access for C-SCALE providers.

C-SCALE installation supported 27 different use cases: six of them were internal to the project, while the other 21 came from the C-SCALE Open Call and the EOSC DIH Expression of Interest for Business Pilots. The installations also provided resources for supporting the activities related to the evaluation testbed for C-SCALE services, the development of the project’s Earth Observation Metadata Query Service (EO-MQS) as well as the maintenance of the project’s website. All these use cases were in different stages of development, from testing and piloting to production, so the consumption of VA varied from one use case to another. The overall consumption of VA in the project has increased over the last period as the number of use cases and their maturity have increased, and thanks to the three-month extension of the project and the adjustment in the available installations, it has reached 47.45% of the total available storage resource and 62.16% of the available processing resources, with both increasing significantly since M24.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the final assessment of the Virtual Access (VA) installations of the project, which provided the computing and storage resources that powered the C-SCALE services already available through EOSC. Deliverable D3.4¹ introduced the VA installations and the initial usage delivered until the end of November 2021, and two updates of the usage collected until the end of Month 18 (June 2022) and Month 24 (December 2022) were provided in Deliverables D3.5² and D3.6³ respectively. This document reports on the status of the VA usage of the providers of C-SCALE at M33, covering the last period of the project and including its three months extension.

The providers collected input until September 15th 2023, therefore some of the numbers will be updated once the project finishes after the end of September 2023. The document reports usage from all the use cases which were supported during the project. Some of them concluded at the end of June 2023 (M30) before the actual project end in M33 as the effort available to continue their development was exhausted.

The lack of VA consumption was identified early in the project as one of possible outcomes of two project risks:

- “Lacking features for supporting use cases in WP4 (User co-design and functional testing of Copernicus data and compute federation)”. Use cases from the project were developed in parallel with the project services, thus the consumption from these was expected to be low in the early phases of the project. A close collaboration with WP4 helped to identify the most relevant features to focus WP3 developments on, but this required a long-iterative process to provide the required functionality that is still in progress. WP4 use cases also took longer to develop than expected and this delayed the scaling-out phase that should have consumed a larger amount of VA resources.
- “Not enough use cases are identified through the Early Adopter Programme”. Although the number of use cases has been growing over the final months of the project due to internal alignment and improvements in service delivery, the consumption of VA from these use cases did not reach a level that allowed for consumption of the VA resources up to the expected targets.

As described in D3.6, a mitigation plan to increase the consumption of VA was put in place: the plan started from a projection of the consumption until the end of the project, considering the maturity of the existing use cases and the new ones in the pipeline. With that information, an amendment was created to shift VA units from underused installations to those more requested to better serve the users. The amendment was signed in M30, and the project introduced several changes in the original 23 installations from the C-SCALE providers to fix calculation errors found in the VA installation description forms. Moreover, it served to adapt the existing resources to the actual demand from the use cases, to better serve our use cases and to increase the capability of the

¹ [D3.4 Periodical assessment of the services V1](#)

² [D3.5 Periodical assessment of the services V2](#)

³ [D3.6 Periodical assessment of the services V3 \(Under EC Review\)](#)

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service providers and their services (installations) to support the user communities until the end of the project and reach the expected target quantity of access. These have been realised by changing the quantity of access units of certain installations, which resulted in changes in the Access Costs on the basis of Unit Cost (total budget for each installation).

The aforementioned installations and changes are summarised in Table 1 below. Changed units in installations are highlighted in bold font. Changes were customised to the use cases supported on every provider: some use cases were more data-intensive and therefore the amount of storage resources of the supporting installation were increased (e.g., EODC), while others were more compute-intensive or delays in their development caused to consume less storage than expected, and therefore the amount of computing resources of the supporting installations were increased (e.g. SURF). Installations with no requests for them, namely MS4 installations of SURF and VITO CVB (Storage), were removed and their budget was transferred to other installations and for additional effort to better support the use cases. A new installation, S3 at CREODIAS, was created to pilot new remote data access modes from other C-SCALE providers.

Table 1. VA installations and changes

VA installation	Initial units	Amended units	Description of the change
EODC EO storage	150 TB*Year	191 TB*Year	Use cases that are onboarded on EODC's infrastructure required more storage capacity than it was initially foreseen. Cloud and HPC resources are sufficient for what these use cases needed.
EODC EO Cloud	620 CPU*Year	470 CPU*Year	
EODC HPC	600,000 CPU*Hour	500,000 CPU*Hour	
MetaCentrumCloud – CPU	2,850 CPU core*month	2,850 CPU core*month	No changes
INFN Bari Storage	1,500 TB*Year	927 TB*Year	Less storage resources have been required due to delays in the use cases that INFN supports.
INFN Bari CPU	3,840 CPU core*month	3,840 CPU core*month	
SURFsara dCache Front end storage	160 TiByte*Year	105 TiByte*Year	MS4 installations were removed as there were no requests for them, and it was found the use cases were served sufficiently by other generic solutions in C-SCALE.
SURFsara Spider (HTDP) Storage	154 TB*Year	154 TB*Year	
SURFsara Data Processing Compute	1,500,00 CPU*Hour	2,001,401 CPU*Hour	
SURFsara MS4 Storage	10 TB*Year	0	The quantity of access of SURFsara dCache Front end storage was decreased as the use cases received and supported, started later than planned and required more code development than expected before they were ready for processing
SURFsara MS4 SSD Storage	96 TB*Month	0	
SURFsara MS4 Compute	147,600 CPU*Hour	0	

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			<p>large data collections. These delays meant that less storage for active data was needed.</p> <p>SURFsara Data Processing Compute installation was increased to cover the CPU consumption from use cases.</p>
VITO CVB (Storage)	266 TB *Month	0	Storage needed for intermediate and end products required minimal intermediate storage capacity. The available capacity was transferred to CPU, enabling VITO to provide more computing resources for openEO to their use cases.
VITO CVB (CPU)	876,000 CPU*hour	1,114,800 CPU*hour	
GRNET KNS - Storage Cloud	250000 TB*Hour	250000 TB*Hour	The change enabled GRNET to provide the required additional support to the use cases that are onboarded on their infrastructure, as it was shown that less ARIS - Compute HPC resources were needed but more technical support.
GRNET KNS - Cloud	1,650,000 Core*Hour	1,650,000 Core*Hour	
GRNET ARIS - Storage HPC	219000 TB*Hour	219000 TB*Hour	
GRNET ARIS - CPU HPC	1,000,000 Core*Hour	423,077 Core*Hour	
CREODIAS - Storage	2762 TB*month	510 TB*month	Transfer of capacity from storage to GPU to meet the demand of GPUs from several use cases onboarded from the open call of C-SCALE. A new S3 installation was created in CREODIAS to support the development and testing of remote access to files from other C-SCALE providers.
CREODIAS - Compute	1,500,000 vCore*hour	1,500,000 vCore*hour	
CREODIAS - GPU	6000 GPU*hour	17,000 GPU*Hour	
CREODIAS - S3	n/a	44 TB	
INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Storage)	450 TB*Month	239 TB*Month	Less storage resources have been required due to delays in the use cases that INCD supported.
INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Compute)	4,500 CPU*month	4,500 CPU*month	

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2 Virtual Access Metrics

Each installation of C-SCALE defined a set of metrics to report VA usage to the project, with a clear description of the metrics and how the measurement was done by the provider. These metrics were reported on a 3-monthly basis to the internal project workspace (Confluence) by the providers.

C-SCALE implemented an SLA (Service Level Agreement)/OLA (Operational Level Agreement) framework that tracked, for all use cases, the agreed number of resources and the conditions to access them. There are agreements in place for all the active use cases within C-SCALE: six use cases from WP4 and 21 use cases from the Open Call and EOSC DIH. Additionally, three support use cases are also covered under these agreements: the EO-MQS, that captures the VA usage for hosting the Earth Observation Metadata Query Service delivered by WP2, the C-SCALE website hosting, and the C-SCALE Evaluation Testbed, which provided an easy access to C-SCALE resources for evaluation and training without the need of submission of a full request via the Open Call. All agreements including Provider, starting and ending dates and use case names are summarised in Table 2. An additional use case was supported at SURF (pangeo-greenness) for initial testing, but it didn't reach a production level and was not included as part of the VA agreements recorded below.

Table 2. C-SCALE VA Agreements

#	Use Case	Acquisition Type	Providers	Start date	End date
1	Aquamonitor	Project	INCD, INFN	2021-06-01	2023-06-30
2	RETURN	Project	SURF, EODC	2021-07-01	2023-09-30
3	LSDA	Project	SURF, EODC	2021-07-01	2023-09-30
4	HiSea	Project	GRNET, CloudFerro	2021-07-01	2023-06-30
5	Wetland Water Stresses	Project	EODC, CloudFerro	2021-11-01	2023-07-31
6	WaterWatch	Project	CESNET, VITO	2022-02-01	2023-09-30
7	SAR on the fly	Open Call	CloudFerro	2022-04-25	2023-09-30
8	SPOTLIGHT	Open Call	EODC	2022-07-01	2023-09-30
9	TWC-SCUP	Open Call	EODC	2022-09-01	2023-09-30
10	In SAR Cubes	Open Call	CESNET	2022-09-01	2023-09-30
11	UDOS	Open Call	EODC	2022-10-19	2023-09-30
12	Coastmonitor	Open Call	INFN	2022-11-01	2023-06-30
13	NC4EC	Open Call	EODC	2022-11-30	2023-09-30
14	GLTFCA	Open Call	INCD, CloudFerro	2022-12-08	2023-09-30
15	KappaMask	Open Call	CloudFerro	2022-12-08	2023-09-30
16	Grapevine	Open Call	CloudFerro	2022-12-13	2023-06-30
17	LOST-Savage	Open Call	INFN, CloudFerro	2023-01-01	2023-09-30
18	Plankton	Open Call	INFN	2023-01-01	2023-06-30
19	NivarIA	Open Call	EODC	2023-01-16	2023-09-30
20	G-PeT	Open Call	GRNET	2023-01-24	2023-06-30

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21	pangeo-reliance	Open Call	CloudFerro	2023-01-26	2023-09-30
22	Geohazards	Open Call	CESNET	2023-01-25	2023-06-30
23	pangeo-julia	Open Call	EODC	2023-01-26	2023-09-30
24	APOLIS2Laserscan	Open Call	EODC	2023-01-01	2023-09-30
25	African Rainfall	Open Call	SURF	2023-01-03	2023-09-30
26	SITO- PS_2023_WBK04	Open Call	EODC	2023-06-01	2023-09-30
27	rmm_salt	Open Call	GRNET	2023-07-20	2023-09-30
28	EO-MQS Hosting	Support	EODC	2022-01-14	2023-09-30
29	C-SCALE Website Hosting	Support	EODC	2021-01-20	2023-09-30
30	C-SCALE Evaluation testbed	Support	CESNET	2022-09-09	2023-09-30

The information in the agreements with the expected usage from the use cases themselves and the usage metrics from providers were used as input for the project's capacity management team formed by members of the *Operations of the Virtual Access installation* task (T3.4) and *Provider onboarding support and the VA coordination* task (T5.1). The team kept track of the usage trends and reacted accordingly and planned the capacity allocation for the supported use cases.

Table 3 shows the cumulative metric values from the start of the project until M11 (as reported in D3.4), until the end of M18 (June 2022), until M24 (December 2022) and until M33 (September 2023), which is the last metrics collection for the project deliverables. Table 3 contains fixes detected in the metrics reported for GRNET and INCD for M01-M18 included in D3.5 (and already corrected in D3.6).

Similar to the previous version D3.6, metrics related to number of users or number of use cases in Table 3 have been homogenized to show the number of use cases supported by each installation and, whenever available, also the number of individual users belonging to the supported use cases. This facilitates the comparison of the uptake of providers as the number of individual users varied depending on the usage model of each use case: from use cases where a single to few expert users were in charge of the deployment of services that final researchers will access, to use cases where each individual user interacted with the installations directly (e.g., by submitting jobs to a HPC system). It is noted that the VA usage, as reported in Table 3, refers to the period from January 2021 (M1) until September 2023 (M33). Those installations with fixed allocation for resources (e.g., for storage volumes) report the consumption until the end of the project, and other installations report until the collection date on September 15th.

Table 3. VA Usage

VA Installation	Metric type	Description	M01-M11	M01-M18	M01-M24	M01-M33
EODC EO storage	Number of users	Number of user accounts	0	1 use case	5 use cases	10 use cases

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	Usage	Allocated TB*year	0	0.42 TB*year	16.80 TB*year	198.67 TB*Year
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries from the user accounts	0	1	3	5
	Names of countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	-	Austria	Austria, Germany, Greece,	Austria, Germany, Greece, Spain, The Netherlands
EODC EO Cloud	Number of users	Number of user accounts	1	1 use case	5 use cases	11 use cases
	Usage	Time of VM usage	1.33 CPU*Year	10.64 CPU*Year	77.97 CPU*year	467.33 CPU*Year
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries from the user accounts	1	1	3	5
	Names of countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	Austria	Austria	Austria, Germany, Greece,	Austria, Germany, Greece, Spain, The Netherlands
EODC HPC	Number of users	Number of user accounts	0	0	0	1 use case
	Usage	CPU hours	0	0	0	112,813 CPU hours
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries from the user accounts	0	0	0	1
	Names of countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	-	-	-	The Netherlands
MetaCentrum Cloud - CPU	Number of users	Number of user consuming CPU resources	0	1 use case (1 user)	3 (16 users)	3 (17 users)

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	Usage	CPU core months consumed (with typically 4GB of RAM per core)	0	10 CPU core/month	524 CPU core/month	2,817 core/month
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries from the user accounts	0	1	3	3
	Names of countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	-	Czechia	Czechia, United Kingdom, The Netherlands	Czechia, United Kingdom, The Netherlands
INFN Bari Storage	Number of user communities	Communities supported by the installation	0	0	2 use cases	2 use cases
	Usage	TB used / month	0	0	0.78 TB month	1.2 TB month
INFN Bari CPU	Number of user communities	Communities supported by the installation	0	0	2 use cases	2 use cases
	Usage	CPU hours	0	0	55.61 CPU month	179 CPU month
SURFsara dCache Front end storage	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	0	0	0	2 use cases (10 users)
	Usage	Number of TB per year consumed by C-SCALE users	0	0	0	145.83 TiB*Year
	Satisfaction ⁴	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	-	-	-	3
SURFsara Spider (HTDP) Storage	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	14	2 use cases (18 users)	2 use cases (29 users)	4 use cases (34 users)

⁴ Measures customer satisfaction based on a feedback survey that grades services from 1-5 (being very dissatisfied and 5 being very satisfied)

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	Usage	Number of TB per year consumed by C-SCALE users	19.15 TB*Year	41.79 TB*year	64.46 TB*Year	104.03 TB*Year
	Satisfaction	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	4	5	5	5
SURFsara Data Processing Compute	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	14	2 use cases (18 users)	2 use cases (29 users)	4 use cases (34 users)
	Usage	Wall time CPU core hours consumed by C-SCALE users	143,599 CPU*hours	247,962 CPU*hours	370,328 CPU*hours	3,240,437 CPU*hours
	Satisfaction	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	4	4	4	4
VITO CVB (CPU)	Number of users	User that logged in to openEO	0	1 use case (5 users)	2 use cases (7 users)	2 use case (7 users)
	Usage	Time in months for VM usage and in hours for Hadoop usage	0	16,660 CPU Hours	276,349 CPU Hours	276,754 CPU Hours
VITO CVB (CPU)	Number of countries reached	Number of countries reached using our datawarehousing system	0	0	1	5
	Names of the countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	-	-	The Netherlands	Belgium, The Netherlands, Portugal, Italy, Austria
GRNET KNS - Storage Cloud	Number of users	Number of users accessing the service	11	1 use case (11 users)	1 use case (11 users)	1 use case (11 users)
	Usage	Total number of TB Hours for the duration of the project	363.40 TB*Hours	894.24 TB*Hours	1,538.98 TB*Hours	3,044.61 TB*Hours

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GRNET KNS - Cloud	Number of users	Number of users accessing the service	11	1 use case (11 users)	1 use case (11 users)	1 use case (11 users)
	Usage	Total number of virtual CPU hours with 2 GB of RAM consumed for the duration of the project	93,137.71 Core*Hours	217,138.03 Core*Hours	353,284.07 Core*Hours	704,716.02 Core*Hours
GRNET ARIS - Storage HPC	Number of users	Number of users accessing the service	5	1 use case (5 users)	1 use case (5 users)	3 use cases (10 users)
	Usage	Total number of TB hours for the duration of the project	1.36 TB*Hours	131.62 TB*Hours	293.03 TB*Hours	31,426.34 TB*Hours
GRNET ARIS - CPU HPC	Number of users	Number of users accessing the service	5	1 use case (5 users)	1 use case (5 users)	3 use cases (10 users)
	Usage	Total number of CPU core hours with 2 GB of RAM consumed for the duration of the project	170 Core*Hours	326 Core*Hours	326 Core*Hours	53,171 Core*Hours
CREODIAS - Storage	Number of users	Users that create an account and logged into OpenStack dashboard or used API services	0	2 use cases (2 users)	5 use cases (7 users)	5 use cases (7 users)
	Usage	Number of credits in pay-per-use model	0	20 TB*Month	58 TB*Month	58 TB*Month
CREODIAS - Compute	Number of users	Users that create an account and	0	2 use cases (2 users)	5 use cases (7 users)	5 use cases (7 users)

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		logged into OpenStack dashboard or used API services				
	usage	Number of credits in pay-per-use model	0	7866,76 vCPU*hours	81800,39 vCPU*hours	313,273.25 vCPU*hours
CREODIAS - GPU	Number of users	Users that create an account and logged into OpenStack dashboard or used API services	0	2 use cases (2 users)	5 use cases (7 users)	5 use cases (7 users)
	Usage	Number of credits in pay-per-use model	0	407.27 VMGPU*hours	617,73 VMGPU*hours	7,816.23 VMGPU*hours
CREODIAS – S3	Number of users	Users that create an account and logged into OpenStack dashboard or used API services	0	0	0	1
	Usage	Number of credits in pay-per-use model	0	0	0	4 TB
INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Storage)	Number of users	Total number of new users	4	1 use case (4 users)	2 use case (5 users)	2 (5 users)
	Usage	Total storage (unit TB*month) allocated to the project	62.015	167 TB*month	201 TB*month	243 TB*month
	Number of countries reached	Total number of new countries	1	1	2	2
	Names of the countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	The Netherlands	The Netherlands	The Netherlands, Zambia	The Netherlands, Zambia

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INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Compute)	Number of users	Total number of new users	4	1 use case (4 users)	2 use case (5 users)	2 (5 users)
	Usage	Total number of virtual VCPU*month with 2 GB of RAM consumed for the duration of the project	431.71 CPU*month	1279.71 CPU*month	2113.41 CPU*month	3339.09 CPU*month
	Number of countries reached	Total number of new countries	1	1	2	2
	Names of the countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	The Netherlands	The Netherlands	The Netherlands, Zambia	The Netherlands, Zambia

Table 4 shows the consumption in percent of the available units for all the installations. Thanks to the Open Call use cases and additional support available from the providers, the consumption has raised over the last months with several providers surpassing the available capacity in the project as Virtual Access. Consumption of resources, especially CPU, continued beyond the reporting on 15th September, therefore some installations will see an increase of their utilisation at the end of the project.

Table 4. VA Consumption

Provider	VA installation	Available units	Consumed M1 – M33
EODC	EODC EO storage	191 TB*year	104.01%
	EODC EO Cloud	470 CPU*year	99.43%
	EODC HPC	500,000 CPU*hour	22.56%
CESNET	MetaCentrumCloud - CPU	2,850 CPU core*month	98.84%
INFN	INFN Bari Storage	927 TB*month	0.13%
	INFN Bari CPU	3840 CPU core*month	4.66%
SURF	SURFsara dCache Front end storage	154 TiByte*Year	86.13%
	SURFsara Spider (HTDP) Storage	105 TB*Year	99.08%
	SURFsara Data Processing Compute	2,001,401 CPU*Hour	161.91%
VITO	VITO CVB (CPU)	371,600 CPU*hour	74.48%
GRNET	GRNET KNS - Storage Cloud	250,000 TB*Hour	1.22%
	GRNET KNS - Cloud	1,650,000 Core*Hour	42.71%

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	GRNET ARIS - Storage HPC	219,000 TB*Hour	14.35%
	GRNET ARIS - CPU HPC	423,077 Core*Hour	12.57%
CloudFerro	CREODIAS - Storage	510 TB*month	11.38%
	CREODIAS - Compute	1,500,000 vCore*hour	20.88%
	CREODIAS - GPU	17,000 VMGPU*hour	45.98%
	CREODIAS - S3	44 TB	9.09%
INCD	INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Storage)	239 TB*month	101.67%
	INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Compute)	4500 CPU*month	99.79%

Figure 1 and Figure 2 depict the consumed CPU hours and TB month (normalised for all providers to the same unit) compared to the available number of units for each installation.

Figure 1. Normalised VA CPU hours for processing installations

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Figure 2. Normalised TB month for Storage installations

Figure 3 shows the percentage of VA consumed per installation type (storage and processing). Until M12 the usage reported was mostly due to testing integration of the providers, in the period M12-M18 the infrastructure has started to be actively used by all the use cases and in M24, the infrastructure started to support a wider number of use cases and hence the consumption increased significantly from M24 onwards. By M33 the providers have kept the support for existing use cases and both storage and CPU usage has kept increasing as expected. The three-month extension has allowed to further consume VA resources, and the consumption has kept growing: the consumption of storage resources raised from 32.27% to 47.45% of the total available storage resources, while processing resources consumption doubled over the last three months of the project reaching 62.16%, even considering that several use cases stopped the usage of the services in M30. Storage usage is still overall lower than CPU usage. In most of the cases this was due to slow start of the use cases during the first half of the project.

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% VA Consumption for installation type

Figure 3. VA Consumption per installation type

2.1 Providers reports

2.1.1 EODC

During the entire lifetime of the project, EODC has supported 11 different use cases and hosted the C-SCALE website and the EO-MQS service on its infrastructure.

Use Cases have diversified in terms of origin (home country) and infrastructural needs: EODC hosted use cases from Austria, Germany, the Netherlands and Spain. Additionally, Virtual Access resource provision has been increasing throughout the project. The Wetland Water Stresses use case implemented by TU Wien, Austria, terminated their activities in June 2023. APOLIS2Laserscan, a use case implemented by Geosphere Austria, terminated the EODC EO Storage installation, while continuing the use of the EODC EO Cloud VA installation. All other use cases continued their activities until project end (30/09/2023). A high demand for training, support or setup instructions was requested from the hosted HPC use cases TWC-SCUP, RETURN and LSDA.

Specific support was given to EODC cloud use cases Pangeo Julia, SITO-PS_2023_WBK04, and the RETURN HPC use case for using Sentinel-1 Analysis Ready Data and Sentinel-2 L1C data produced and collected by EODC. Furthermore NC4EC, SPOTLIGHT, TWC-SCUP and APOLIS2Laserscan have created high-impact success stories and outreach items nationally and internationally that showcase the success of using C-SCALE VA resources for their projects. Specific support was given when needed to all cloud use cases, especially when high-load multiprocessing was expected (APOLIS2Laserscan) or operational systems required EODC to engage with the setup (TWC-SCUP).

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Lastly, EODC continues to host the C-SCALE website and the Earth Observation Metadata Query Service (EO-MQS) on their EODC EO Cloud installation, which enables EO SC and beyond users to request the sustainable services of C-SCALE.

2.1.2 CESNET

CESNET has been supporting three separate use cases, or modes of usage of the compute resources. Firstly, the WaterWatch use case, whose initial stages (until M18) consisted mostly of preparatory work and prototyping of data cataloguing and discovery solutions, and from there onwards the resources have been used for data discovery and analysis. Waterwatch consumed resources primarily through an on-demand deployment of an OpenEO cluster, and also through STAC metadata processing. Secondly, CESNET has been supporting the C-SCALE Evaluation Virtual Organisation (VO), which is a low-threshold entry VO for users wishing to evaluate C-SCALE's interactive or cloud environments. Especially in the latter half of the project, resources allocated to this VO have been used for hands-on training, and evaluation of the use of Jupyter Notebooks (i.e., the interactive analysis platform) in C-SCALE. Thirdly there was the In-SAR-Cubes use case, which commenced operation in fall 2022 and has been using allocated cloud resources for Sentinel-1 sliding aperture radar interferometry analysis.

2.1.3 INFN

INFN has implemented the two use cases Aquamonitor and Coastmonitor over the INFN services and resources. In particular, the activity was focused on implementing the use case frameworks in the INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator with the aim of using not only INFN resources to automatically deploy services, but also other providers both public (AWS, Azure, etc) and/or private (EGI federated cloud providers). The VA consumption of INFN is associated to this initial support activity.

2.1.4 SURF

SURF has been supporting four use cases (i) *REcovery of Tropical Forest Using Radar seNtinel time series* (RETURN), (ii) *High Resolution Land Surface Drought Analysis* (LSDA), (iii) *Pangeo-Greenness* and (iv) *AfricaRain* in the period M1-33. The RETURN use case, as previously reported, shifted its focus from Sentinel-2 to Sentinel-1 (S-1) radar data. Significant human support by SURF was provided to RETURN to match the S-1 processing case to the HTC cluster and allow for scale-up in a largely automated fashion. This was done successfully, and in addition SURF also provided support for finding and re-submitting failed (typically due to network or filesystem errors) jobs through a streamlined process. Significant additional testing was also done by RETURN to investigate and resolve data issues. The individual jobs took longer than initially expected which together with additional testing meant a higher-than-expected usage for this use case. At the time of writing a significant part of the Amazon basin has been processed. To safeguard the data and results SURF provided additional storage for RETURN via the dCache installation.

For the LSDA case, SURF has continued to provide support and engaged in user meetings. The LSDA use case achieved an excellent scale-up at SURF. The LSDA workflow ran smoothly on the SURF provided infrastructure, however it was affected by a small percentage of job failures due to

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network and filesystem issues. Through rescheduling the failed jobs, LSDA managed to finish their proposed work within the C-SCALE project (in part due to the project extension until Sep. 30th 2023). This rescheduling, in addition with the extension, meant that LSDA used more resources than initially foreseen. LSDA also managed to re-deploy their (SURF) processing workflow to the TUW/EODC HPC in a straightforward manner thereby showing the portability of this solution achieved in C-SCALE across HPC and HTC clusters.

In 2023 two additional use cases, Pangeo-Greenness and AfricaRain, were provisioned at SURF. To support Pangeo-Greenness SURF provided two additional high memory nodes with 60 CPU cores each were provided. For AfricaRain SURF provided dCache storage and access to Data Processing.

The SURF VA installations related to MS4 haven't delivered any VA resources as no use cases were found for this specialistic functionality. To avoid wasting these resources, the MS4 installations were removed from the project in amendment.

2.1.5 VITO

VITO has supported the use of openEO in their installations for the WaterWatch and Aquamonitor use cases. Besides the provisioning of resources, VITO has provided extensive support for porting the use cases to the openEO framework ensuring the applications could run on the C-SCALE providers, as well as supporting the providers in configuring the openEO system on their infrastructures. In the frame of both WaterWatch and Aquamonitor, a Kubernetes cluster on CreoDIAS, with access to multiple large EO data archives (Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2) was used to test scalability and data access performance, allowing to work concurrently while other providers were still working on provisioning of EO-data and configuring the openEO system on Kubernetes. For functional, small-scale, testing of both use cases the openEO instance in Terrascope has been used.

VITO implemented various improvements to help in the deployment of openEO on C-Scale IAAS:

1. Support for authenticated reading from object storage (S3)
2. Support for load_stac, giving compatibility with the C-Scale data federation (EO-MQS), and supporting deployments without preconfigured (local) collections
3. Security improvements for Kubernetes
4. Successfully tested and rolled out Rancher as a generic auto-scaling solution.
5. Most openEO backend settings have been made configurable.

In addition, VITO improved the openEO federation with important contributions to the openEO aggregator component. The main improvement is the ability to use collections from different openEO backends in the same process graph.

2.1.6 GRNET

GRNET has been actively supporting – in terms of resources and technical support – the HiSea use case, for the period M01-M33. The VA submission concerns dates until 15 of September. Two major facilities are provided: Cloud and HPC, both delivering CPU and storage resources. On the cloud, one VM with 16 cores is used for the pre- and post-processing in the use case and a second VM is deployed as an NFS-Server with an additional 300 TB storage for data caching. Additionally, a STAC

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endpoint is deployed and registered in the GOCDDB. Moreover, in the HPC infrastructure, HiSea users have already access to run jobs on both the “thin” nodes⁵ (20 cores per node), and the “fat” nodes partition of the HPC infrastructure⁶ (40 cores per node). The VA consumption in this HPC infrastructure is attributable to the setup and testing of the system, such as calculating the scalability and the performance efficiency of the production code using Singularity⁷ containers. Additionally, users from the G-Pet use case had accessed and used the GPU nodes⁸ to execute their experiments. Finally, the utilization of CPU power from GRNET HPC resources has allowed the last use case, under the abbreviation rmm_salt, to tackle complex computations and data analysis tasks, driving substantial advancements in its research and outcomes.

2.1.7 CloudFerro

During M01-M33, CloudFerro became the resource provider of six projects: *Wetland Water Stress*, *SAR on the fly*, *HiSea*, *KappaMask*, *Grapevine* and *Pangeo RELIANCE*. CloudFerro provides GPU for the following projects: SAR on the Fly, Wetland Water Stress, KappaMask and Pangeo RELIANCE, which helps to get results faster for their needs. The HiSea project started in August 2022 and has only been running on CPU. Three newest projects KappaMask, Grapevine, and Pangeo RELIANCE have been using CloudFerro compute infrastructure as well. Additionally, a new kind of installation for delivering remote data access using S3 interface was created under C-SCALE VA. This installation supports downloading data to other providers of the federation to enable the distributed processing of data. The S3 installation has been piloted by AquaMonitor with INCD downloading data as needed to support the use case.

2.1.8 INCD

INCD has deployed a Kubernetes cluster on top of an OpenStack to support C-SCALE use cases. The Kubernetes cluster comprises 10 nodes with 16 cores and 32 GB of RAM each where openEO is deployed. The initial approach was to create a single volume of 12TB for the storage of data for the Aquamonitor use case. This setup was later changed to a S3 bucket that is mounted on every single compute node, allowing for the sharing of data both within the cluster and the outside world. A helm chart recipe was also developed for the deployment of a local resto STAC server, used to download satellite imagery products directly to an S3 Bucket which is then used by openEO. It was also necessary to develop a Python program to register the metadata of the downloaded products from the CESNET STAC catalogue. This allowed that data stored at the INCD S3 bucket is also discoverable from the CESNET catalogue. A Jupyter notebook was developed with the collaboration of VITO to test the INCD endpoint. At the same time, the Kubernetes cluster deployment was improved by using kubespray recipes integrated into GitLab pipelines. Besides the Aquamonitor use case INCD also provided support during M22-M30 for the Great Limpopo Trans-Frontier Conservation Area (GLTFCA) use case. We also want to emphasise that INCD will continue to support

⁵ See technical description of nodes at <https://doc.aris.grnet.gr/system/hardware/#thin-nodes>

⁶ See technical description of nodes at <https://doc.aris.grnet.gr/system/hardware/#fat-nodes>

⁷ <https://sylabs.io/singularity>

⁸ See technical description of nodes at <https://doc.aris.grnet.gr/system/hardware/#gpu-nodes>

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the C-SCALE service through their OpenEO endpoint which is now accessible through the C-SCALE Earth Observation Metadata Query Service (EO-MQS).

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3 Green Computing

C-SCALE WP3’s manages the Tier-1 aspects of Green Computing of the project, defined as follows:

Tier 1: Analysis of the “Direct environmental OPEX” of C-SCALE by tracking the energy consumption of the computing centres. Monitoring of the KPIs (PUE and REF) defined in the EN-50600-4⁹ across as many of the computing centres as possible and the use of additional indicators (such as reuse of the heat of the computing centre or carbon intensity of the electricity supply) where available.

Table 5 reports the available metrics for the providers for the green computing aspects wherever these are available. These were already reported in D3.5 and are repeated here for the sake of completion.

Table 5. Green Computing aspects of the providers

Provider	Metrics	Comments
EODC	PUE: 1.22 ¹⁰ REF: 0.67 ¹¹	<p>Efficiency and environmentally responsible computing are a strong theme at EODC.</p> <p>To support this, the following measures are considered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power supplies for storage and compute systems are either 80 Plus Platinum rated, or equivalent, following compliance with Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/424 (Directive 2009/125/EC). • The primary datacentre makes use of a free cooling setup completed in 2019. This is further enhanced with turbo technology, whereby exhaust airflow is used to further improve efficiency. <p>The latest iteration of EODC HPC, based on the VSC-5 ranks at 90 in the Green 500 – An international ranking of supercomputer power efficiently – and offers 4.48 Gflops/Watt¹²</p>
CESNET	PUE: 1.6	CESNET actively monitors energy consumption of production clusters.

⁹ CENELEC EN 50600-4-1:2016 Information technology - Data centre facilities and infrastructures - Part 4-1: Overview of and general requirements for key performance indicators
https://standards.cenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=CENELEC:110:::FSP_PROJECT,FSP_ORG_ID:60776,1258297&cs=1EE9B4ACAAF98EFCDA91E2949FBE95F1E

¹⁰ PUE calculation excluded energy efficiency of the IT load, its utilisation or productivity.

¹¹ The REF calculation refers to the entire building where the datacentre is hosted

¹² See <https://www.top500.org/lists/green500/2022/06/>

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INFN	n/a	INFN is actively studying measures to implement a green approach on running the ReCaS-Bari Data Centre. INFN is planning the implementation of a direct free cooling solution inside the data centre. In the short term INFN is deeply investing time in studying the optimization on cooling systems depending on the status of usage of the IT resources.
SURF	PUE: 1.22 REF: 1	SURF tracks energy consumption of the data centres hosting C-SCALE workloads and is actively working on tracking the carbon footprint of the infrastructure. SURF is not in direct control of the PUE and REF metrics of the data centres as SURF acts as a tenant for those.
VITO	n/a	VITO's computing resource supplier has Class 3 Compliant design with EN 50600. Moreover, with continuous performance improvements through OpenEO, VITO is aiming to reduce the need for computing resources for EO data processing.
GRNET	PUE: 1.6	GRNET is actively working on tracking the carbon footprint of the infrastructure, while it measures the energy consumption of the data centres that deliver all the workloads.
CloudFerro	PUE: 1.65	CloudFerro's data centre for provisioning C-Scale resources has Class 3 Compliant design with EN 50600.
INCD	PUE: 1.45	Since the early start of the INCD, reducing the carbon footprint of the infrastructure is one of the major goals. To accomplish this, over the last years, a series of investments and procedures have been implemented on the operational data centre. The measures were: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Installation of new racks and replacement of the old supply circuits with new Power Distribution Units (PDU), with real-time consumption measures. The new PDU's effectively increase the efficiency of data centre power usage. ● Inclusion in public tendering specifications, CPU power consumption (SPEC per watt) and power supplies with 80 Plus Titanium certification. ● Implementation of free-cooling, requiring a re-design of the cooling system and chillers replacements by new units optimized to the climate conditions (subtropical in the case of Lisbon, Portugal).

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4 INFRAEOSC-07 VA Assessment report

The External Advisory Board for the VA assessment of the INFRAEOSC-07 projects has been established in line with the GA requirements and in agreement with the EC and is composed by one representative from each INFRAEOSC-07 project. After a first assessment, with the aim to check and discuss and provide recommendations on the VA practices and methodologies of each project (held in December 2022), a second assessment was carried out in June 2023.

The objective of the second assessment has been to share gained experiences on the application of the VA methods and principles in the provisioning of the different offered services and to define common lessons learnt.

A plenary meeting took place online on the 1st of June 2023. During the meeting, each INFRAEOSC-07 project representative presented the advantages and challenges in the application of the VA rules and principles to the specific service offering, and commonalities/differences were discussed among the board members.

Common lessons learnt have then been agreed and are summarized as follows.

First of all, the VA method is valued as an instrument to allow the service providers to recover the costs of used resources and services. The VA method also allows to provide the services free-at-the-point of use, even in the case of usually pay per use ones, offering the possibility to users and communities to test and start the take up of the services at no costs thus reducing the adoption barrier. It is also acknowledged that it is important to have both investment and operational costs included as part of the units cost calculation, even if not all operational costs can be claimed by all providers depending on the specific site accounting rules.

However, being the VA method new in its application for some categories of services and providers part of the INFRAEOSC-07 projects, some challenges have been identified. Overcoming these issues in future EC funded projects would make the instrument even more important and effective.

Only in few cases the VA costs were based on actual costs method only, while in most of the cases unit costs or a combination of unit and actual costs was used. The right choice of unit is thus vital to allow a meaningful representation of the services usage, but in many cases the proper unit type was difficult to define at the start of the project. At the same time, the unit costs are defined at the proposal writing phase and during the projects' execution years, many costs might change (the high increase in electricity costs of the last year is just one example). However, in the current implementation of the VA model, updates in the type and cost of units imply the need to request an amendment to the GA, which is making the process time consuming. This lack of flexibility in the VA budget management makes it also difficult to adjust the VA offering to changes in the needs from the users' communities during the projects, for example by updating the quantity of units being offered, transferring units from one installation to another, removing or adding new installations.

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As already mentioned, the INFRAEOSC-07 projects collect together in their offering very diverse types of services, with different units/metrics and offered by different providers. This led to the impossibility to have a generic and automatic acquisition of the accounting data which implied in many cases to set-up manual collection of the VA accounting data; as always in manual data collection, this is time consuming and prone to errors. At the same time, the recent creation of the possibility for EOSC users to request bundles of services (from different providers but also across different projects) raised the issue on how to properly account those requests (as individual requests vs aggregated information). Another critical element related to the VA accounting is the GA requirement to maintain information needed for auditing for at least 5 years after the project ends; while logs and metrics are collected by each project, it is felt that the procedures and requirements for auditing purposes are not currently sufficiently clear (which level of details of information/logs to maintain and at which level (project level vs provider level)).

With respect to the users/communities being served, it became evident that commitment from large communities is difficult to achieve due to the short-term duration of the projects and support to the VA methods. The short-term VA supported offering is also perceived as discouraging for individual researchers and small groups who will not be able to pay for services via their institutions. This issue becomes particularly relevant for some categories of services like those related to data storage where the expected preservation is normally in the range of 5 to 10 years or even more. It should be also noted that having a lot of small users instead of large communities uptaking the service implies providing much more time for users' support and engagement which might impact on the budget actual costs of the VA installations.

In summary, the INFRAEOSC-07 projects recommendations are:

- The actual cost model is in general easier to account and claim with respect to unit costs;
- More flexible procedures to update the VA offering would be advisable;
- Clearer information on the VA auditing process and requirements would be useful;
- Longer term support to the VA mechanism would reduce the barrier to adoption and make the researchers and communities more keen to update the offered services.

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5 Conclusions

All C-SCALE Virtual Access providers are now engaged with use cases of the project. The conditions and resources available for each use case are captured on Virtual Access Agreements documents, ensuring customers and providers have clear expectations on the delivered service and support the capacity planning of the project.

C-SCALE delivered VA resources through 20 different installations on 8 different providers, covering processing (CPU and GPU), storage and data transfer (S3). The list of installations and the available capacity was adjusted in M30 (June 2023) to adapt to the actual needs of the use cases and allow for better usage of the available resources. Although the usage did not reach the expected targets initially set in the project, the consumption rate increased significantly over the last months due to the higher maturity of the services and the streamlining of the support process of C-SCALE use cases, which allowed for a shorter time for use cases to be able to exploit the resources for their results. In general, the use cases needed more support than initially planned to reach the expected consumption of resources. In M30, the amendment increased the available effort for supporting use cases which also helped to increase the usage of the available services.

C-SCALE has defined a set of services, described and accessible through C-SCALE website¹³, powered by the installations listed in this deliverable. Specifically: the Federated Earth System Simulation and Data Processing Platform (FedEarthData), the Earth Observation - Metadata Query Service (EO-MQS), and the openEO Platform are supported by C-SCALE providers. These are already on-boarded in EOSC and can be ordered by external customers. The mechanisms for service delivery (different from VA) are currently under discussion by the project consortium.

C-SCALE participated in the External Advisory Board for the VA assessment of the INFRAEOSC-07 projects with one representative. This board performed two series of assessments meetings. The first assessment, performed during December 2022, checked the correct application of the VA practices and provided recommendations for each project. C-SCALE implementation and operation of the VA was found well-managed and in line with the requirements. For the second assessment, a common report was produced and added to this document as Section 4. In summary, the Advisory Board found that the VA model is adequate for delivering services to users, although some improvements should be put in place: (i) a more flexible procedure for updating the offer and thus allowing for faster and better adaptation to actual use cases; (ii) clearer information on the audit process and requirements to avoid misunderstandings and potential issues in the reporting; and (iii) longer-term support for the services to reduce the barrier to adoption and make the services more attractive to communities.

¹³ <https://c-scale.eu/services/>

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